

EXTENT OF UTILIZATION OF INNOVATIVE TEACHING STRATEGIES IN MATHEMATICS AND PUPILS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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Extent of Utilization of Innovative Teaching Strategies in Mathematics and Pupils' Academic Performance

Roderick S. Cabrera

Department of Education, Philippines

Corresponding author email: roderickcabrera12@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study examined math performance in a school district under creative teaching approaches. It looked at the age, sex, marital status, highest degree, years of teaching, and seminars attended by mathematics teachers. Among the innovative teaching strategies were small group learning, problem-solving, models and manipulatives, and games. The study also examined teachers' traits, use of these strategies, and pupils' academic performance. From 154 pupils and five math teachers, questionnaires and first-quarter grades were gathered using a descriptive survey and descriptive-comparative approach. Frequency counts, percentages, and the Chi-square test helped evaluate hypotheses. Late thirty-something academics most often were men, married, with masters. Most teachers with 1-5 years of experience have not attended a few seminars. Teachers and pupils used creative ideas like small group learning, problem-solving, models and manipulatives, and games. Strong relationships between teachers' problem-solving and model/manipulative strategies and their sex, marital status, and maximum educational level were found by the study. No significant relationship was found between game or small group learning strategies and teachers' traits. Though the pupils' academic performance is commendable, the study revealed no appreciable correlation between innovative teaching strategies and academic success.

Keywords: innovative teaching strategies, teaching strategies, mathematics performance

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INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is one of humanity's outstanding achievements. By enhancing the human mind's capabilities, Mathematics has facilitated the development of science, technology, engineering, business, and government. Mathematics is also an intellectual achievement of great sophistication and beauty that epitomizes the power of deductive reasoning. For people to participate fully in society, they must know essential mathematics. Innumeracy deprives them not only of the opportunity but also of competence in everyday tasks.

K to 12 is a flagship program of the Department of Education that aims to attune 21st-century learners to the Basic Education Sector Reform. This program focuses on the shift from teacher-centered instruction to pupil-centered instruction. A critical consideration in attaining this is the strategies used by the teacher. This is supported by various recently published documents stating that the key to achieving this goal is teachers' teaching strategies. Mathematics has the following roles in Philippine Education: facilitating participation in productive life activities, providing a way of making sense of the world, serving as a means of communication, and operating as a gateway to national progress. Helping pupils reach their full potential is necessary for the present and future of education. Innovative teaching is necessary for all teachers to meet the educational needs of the new generations (Joson, 2008; Estrella, 2024).

According to Vistro–Yu, excellence in teaching mathematics is the desired goal of our future teachers. The Philippine Council of Mathematics Teachers Educators (MATHTED), Inc. and the Science Education Institute of the Department of Science and Technology present a framework for Philippine Mathematics Teacher Education to open more eyes, minds, and hearts for all to work together for a brighter future for teachers and secure life for the children. Filipinos' mathematics performance reflects Filipinos' deteriorating competency in the increasingly technological global marketplace.

According to the Congressional Commission on Science, Technology, and Engineering (COMSTE), Filipinos in Science and Mathematics ranked low based on varied factors affecting the performance of pupils in Mathematics, one of which is the innovative strategies used by the teacher in teaching Mathematics. Innovative teaching strategies, such as small group discussion, problem-solving, models/manipulatives, and games/simulations, help pupils learn mathematics. This claim was supported by the study of Biggayan (2022), who said these innovative teaching strategies affected pupils' achievement in mathematics. Thus, this study's results may encourage the utilization of more modern, effective, and valuable teaching strategies.

Limitations

This study focused on the extent of utilization of innovative teaching strategies in Mathematics of Baggao West District. The study's respondents are all grade VI Mathematics teachers and pupils of Unit III of Baggao West District. The variables to include are the profiles of Grade VI Mathematics teachers in terms of age, sex, marital status, educational attainment, number of years teaching mathematics, and number of hours of seminars/training related to mathematics attended. The innovative teaching strategies included in the study are commonly used in the classroom setting, according to the researcher's experience. These are the following: small group discussion, problem-solving, models/manipulatives, and games.

Statement of the Problem

The relationship between teachers' profiles, the extent of utilization of innovative teaching strategies, and the relationship between the extent of utilization of innovative teaching strategies and pupils' academic performance in Mathematics was determined. The pupils' academic performance was based on their first grade in mathematics, for it is the latest rating given during the study conducted from August 2023 to December 2023.

Research Questions

The study generally aimed to determine the extent of utilization of innovative teaching strategies in Mathematics. Specifically, it sought the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the mathematics teacher-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age
 - 1.2 sex
 - 1.3 marital status
 - 1.4 highest educational attainment.
 - 1.5 number of years teaching Mathematics and
 - 1.6 Number of hours Seminars/training related to Mathematics attended?
2. What is the extent of utilization of the following innovative teaching strategies adopted by the teachers in Mathematics as assessed by the mathematics teachers and their pupils:
 - 2.1. Small Group Learning Strategy.
 - 2.2. Problem Solving strategy;
 - 2.3. Using Models/Manipulative; and
 - 2.4. Games.
3. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the teacher respondent and their extent of utilization of innovative teaching strategies?
4. What is the academic performance of pupil respondents in Mathematics?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of utilization of innovative strategies and pupils' academic performance in Mathematics?

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses guide the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between the profile of the teacher's respondents and their extent of utilization of innovative teaching strategies.
2. There is no significant relationship between the extent to which innovative strategies are utilized and pupils' academic performance in Mathematics.

Literature Review

This chapter presents the related literature and studies the researchers consider necessary, especially in clarifying the concepts, principles, and theories used as references in this study.

Personal Profile

Soriano (2022) says that Ordoná's study found several things that improve teachers' work. The results show that teachers with more schooling and more years of experience are both better at their jobs, especially when it comes to teaching in the classroom. Teachers prepared for civil service are more likely to get things done than temporary or substitute teachers. Finally, middle school teachers are better at their jobs than elementary school teachers. It was interesting to learn that female teachers were better at their jobs than male teachers, even though they both made the same amount of money. Also, married teachers got more work than single teachers. According to Agliwan (2020), kids who have teachers who have been teaching longer tend to do better in school, especially when there is less stress in the family. Agliwan (2020) also mentioned Taylan (2020), who discovered that personal characteristics did not significantly impact a teacher's ability. Delson, quoted by Soriano in 2022, said that performance improves with age until middle age. He also said that level of education was a key sign of job success. Soriano talked about Alvares in 2022. Alvares also said that workers with more education are better at their jobs and have better attitudes. On the other hand, Bacha's (2020) study on math skills found that gender and marital situation do not significantly affect how well someone does in math. Some personal and professional factors affect how well you teach and do your job, but those factors may change depending on the setting and the subject.

Teaching Strategies

Referring to Aquino (2013), Biggayan (2022) underlines how K to 12 mathematics teaching strategies gain from harmonizing with children's learning preferences, whether visual, auditory, or sensory. In comparison, some pupils find conventional methods more effective, as NCTM (2001) suggests new solutions emphasize dynamic situations that mix technology and cooperative learning. Recent research highlights the need for teachers to think about their strategies and include their pupils in mathematics (Ellis, 2009; Antony & Walshaw, 2009). Mathematical curiosity is encouraged depending on a prepared, empathetic teacher (Joson, 2008). Bruce (2009) and Wu (2014) describe instructional innovation as using many technologically sophisticated strategies to excite pupils' curiosity and enhance learning. Lin (2011) claims that creative education demands reflection and an open mind so pupils can develop ethically and critically. Using ICT tools in rural areas (Cariaga et al., 2024) and enabling adaptive learning throughout the pandemic (Cariaga, 2022), innovative strategies assist in tackling intellectual and emotional obstacles in mathematics education (Har Harriet, 2024). Further mentioned by Halaissi et al. (2023) and Ginoo et al. (2023) are the benefits of pupil-centered methods, including problem-solving, peer collaboration, and self-assessment, which lessen anxiety and enhance academic performance. Including 21st-century skills (Cariaga, 2024; Gerodias et al., 2024) and supporting self-regulated learning (Gerodias, 2024) might help teachers improve pupil performance. Estrella (2024) emphasizes pupil-driven learning projects promoting critical thinking and involvement, particularly in STEM fields. These few strategies provide more responsive and effective learning environments.

Small Group Discussion

One difficulty facing educators today is meeting the needs of individual learners. The traditional classroom now encompasses a range of mixed abilities among pupils – some struggling to meet grade-level standards to those performing above grade level. Slavin, Lake, and Groff (2010) state that small-group learning is the most effective teaching strategy for improving pupil achievement. Small groups differentiate instruction from struggling pupils, pupils having difficulty with just one skill or concept, to those advancing quickly through the material and needing new challenges. Store's (2014) "Developing Mathematical Practices: Small Group Discussions" study is consistent with the present study's findings. Small group discussions determine the quality of whole group discussions and the opportunities for pupils' mathematical thinking. These practices include expecting and assessing pupils' understanding of their peers' strategies and giving them a responsibility to make them accessible to others.

Problem-Solving

Since one of the main functions of school is to provide pupils with skills they need to better adapt to the environment, an essential goal for schools would be to increase pupils' ability to recognize problems and their causes, come up with alternative solutions to problems, demonstrate flexibility and

creativity in thinking and problem-solving, and assume a certain amount of responsibility for problems they encounter (Getubig, 2011). The idea of Van de Walle, as cited by Biggayan 2022, explores problem-solving in elementary classrooms while focusing on how children use (perform tasks) manipulative tools in problem-solving while working on mathematical tasks is right. Ways for teachers to assess children's learning through performance-based tool (manipulative) use will also be examined, and suggestions will be made on the proper use time. Current research reveals that teachers need to teach and assess children's mathematical knowledge in ways that will allow them to show (perform) what they understand. Moreover, teachers must be able to see beyond obvious correct or incorrect answers in children's thinking processes by testing with tests that allow pupils to show what they know. The findings were consistent with the study of Bernardo (2005).

Models/Manipulatives

Studies of mathematics education have long endorsed using manipulatives; associations such as the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM) emphasize their significance. In Soriano (2022), Boggan underlines that while manipulatives have been necessary for decades, some teachers still need to learn to integrate them into their lessons. Boggan's studies show the advantages of using manipulatives and provide guidelines on their suitable usage to enhance mathematics teaching significantly. Likewise, Soriano (2022) mentions Johnson's studies demonstrating how long-term manipulative use improves math skills and changes pupils' perspectives. Manipulatives reduce arithmetic anxiety, increase flexible thinking, and help children understand challenging mathematical concepts. However, Practical use requires teacher interaction to sustain emphasis on the essential mathematical ideas and narrow the gap between the abstract conceptions under the teaching and the actual manipulatives. Biggayan (2022) further notes that Sabean and Bavaria agree that manipulatives should be used deliberately over a long period to increase pupils' understanding most effectively. Moreover, research by Enki (2014) indicates that employing manipulatives enhances pupils' academic performance and makes learning more enjoyable, fostering positive impressions of arithmetic lessons. Many studies confirm that manipulatives increase academic performance, pupil participation, and interest in mathematics classrooms (Clement, 1999; Kayma, 2010; Sowell, 1989; Tuncer, 2008; Yağcı, 2010).

Games

As cited by Biggayan 2022, Dede said that games and simulations can create local contexts that similarly engage learners at home, in school, or after-school programs. At the same time, however, research has shown that the surrounding context can significantly shape how a learner interacts with a simulation or game and the extent to which this interaction supports science learning (Linn et al., 2010). The most important psychological difference between using a simulation or game at school or college and using it informally is the motivation. In formal education, the professor or teacher requires the pupils to interact with the simulation or game, and the pupils may or may not be motivated. In informal contexts, individuals play a game or manipulate a simulation for fun, motivated by their interest and enjoyment.

An Effective Mathematics Environment

Effective learning environments help pupils to develop deep and transferable knowledge. Research from cognitive, social, and developmental psychology and neuroscience supports these founded in learner-centered, community-centered, assessment-centered, and knowledge-centered principles (NRC, 2010) settings, supporting every pupil's growth. Pupils are urged under a community-centered learning environment to challenge one another, share ideas, and collectively improve their knowledge. This promotes openness and gives general (NRC, 2010) the learning process top priority—through errors. Learner-centered environments also emphasize valuing pupils' prior knowledge, experiences, and identities and assisting them to extend them while they acquire new knowledge (Driver et al., 2014).

On the other hand, assessment-centered environments focus on helping pupils monitor and regulate their learning through comments and opportunities for self-evaluation (White & Frederickson, 2008). Teachers generally create and maintain these environments, so continual and improved teacher training becomes even more crucial. Linking theory to practice in teacher training programs assures that teachers are well-prepared to meet the criteria of pupils and the educational system (NCTM, 2001).

These components, taken together, provide a logical framework for promoting optimal learning in which pupils are free to engage with the materials and control their learning process actively.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive survey technique and descriptive correlational design. It is a descriptive survey technique because it uses a questionnaire checklist to gather the pertinent data regarding the profile variables of the teacher respondent and the extent of utilization of innovative teaching strategies in Mathematics. It is considered descriptive correlational design because the profile of teacher respondents was correlated to the extent of utilization of innovative teaching strategies in Mathematics. The relationship between the extent of utilization of innovative teaching strategies in Mathematics and the pupil's academic performance was determined.

Respondents

The study was conducted in the Baggao West District, particularly in all the elementary schools of Unit III. The respondents' study included Bagunot Elementary School, Bunugan Elementary School, Callao Elementary School, Carupian Elementary School, and Taguig Integrated School.

Sampling

All grade VI Mathematics teachers and Grade VI pupils of Unit III school of Baggao West District for the school year 2023 – 2024 were taken as respondents of this study, with five teachers and 154 pupils. Complete or total enumeration was used among the teachers and pupils of Unit III schools of Baggao West District. The distribution of respondents is shown below:

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

SCHOOLS	TEACHERS	PUPILS	TOTAL
Bagunot Elementary School	1	31	32
Bunugan Elementary School	1	36	37
Callao Elementary School	1	18	19
Carupian Elementary School	1	36	37
Taguig Integrated School	1	33	34
TOTAL PARTICIPANTS	5	154	159

Instruments of the Study

The primary tool used in gathering the needed data is a questionnaire. There were two parts of the questionnaire. Part I covered the profile of the mathematics teacher-participants in terms of age, sex, marital status, educational attainment, number of years in teaching mathematics, and number of hours of seminars/training related to mathematics attended. Part II comprised the extent of utilization of innovative teaching strategies adopted by the teachers in Mathematics as assessed by the groups of participants, namely Small Group Learning, Problem Solving, Using Models/Manipulatives, and Games. Another instrument used was the first grading grade of pupil respondents to determine their academic performance in Mathematics. This is termed documentary analysis. The researcher lifted and modified the questionnaires from the Biggayan 2022 study. Due to some modifications/revisions to the questionnaire, the researcher subjected them to the scrutiny of the Mathematics and English Master teachers for validity.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher asked permission to conduct the study. After this was granted, he prepared the needed questionnaire. The researcher personally administered and retrieved the questionnaire. Before administering the questionnaire, the respondents were briefed on how to answer. Informal interviews were also conducted to supplement the responses gathered through the questionnaire.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher sought permission from the school head to obtain a copy of the first grading grade of the pupils' respondents for the school year 2023 – 2024.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of teacher respondents regarding age. The table shows that of 5 respondents, 2 or 40% are in the 35 to 40 age range. This is followed by age ranges from 30 to 35 with a frequency of 2 or 40%, and 1 or 20% of the respondents are in the 25 to 29 age range. The oldest among the respondents is 39, while the youngest is 25. They are generally young, with a mean age of 33.4. They are relatively young, dynamic, and capable of carrying out the task of teaching.

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Teacher – Respondents in terms of age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
36 – 40	2	40 %
Were between 35 and 40. This	5	100 %

Mean = 33.4

Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage of the respondents between 25 and 29 respondents; 3, or 60 %, are males, and 2, or 40 %, are females.

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Teacher – Respondents in Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	3	60 %
Female	2	40 %
Total	5	100 %

Table 4 reveals teacher respondents' frequency and percentage distribution regarding marital status. The table shows that out of 5 teacher respondents, most are married, with a frequency of 4 or 80 %, and 1 or 20 % are single. It can be observed that married Mathematics Teachers outnumbered their single counterparts. The data could be attributed to most respondents being years of age and above.

Table 4. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Teacher – Respondents in Marital Status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	1	20 %
Married	4	80 %
Total	5	100 %

Table 5 illustrates the frequency and percentage distribution of the teacher respondents in terms of educational attainment. The table reveals that most of the respondents had M.A. Units, which constituted 3 or 60 % of the respondents. This is followed by graduates with master's degrees with a frequency of 1 or 20 % and Doctoral Degree units with a frequency of 1 or 20%.

Table 5. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Teacher–respondents in Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
With M.A. Units	3	60 %
Master's Degree Graduate	1	20 %
With Doctoral Degree Units	1	20 %
Total	5	100 %

Table 6 shows teacher respondents' frequency and percentage distribution regarding the years they have taught mathematics. The table reveals that out of 5 respondents, 3, or 60 %, have taught the subject for 1 to 5 years, while 2, or 40 %, have taught the subject for 6 to 10 years.

Table 6. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Teacher – Respondents in Number of Years Teaching Mathematics.

Number of Years Teaching Mathematics	Frequency	Percentage
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1 – 5	3	60 %
6 – 10	2	40 %
Total	5	100 %

Table 7 illustrates the frequency and percentage distribution of teacher respondents regarding the number of hours of seminar/training attended. Three or 60 % of teachers had attended at least nine hours of seminars. On the other hand, 2 or 40 % of teachers had 9 to 40 hours at seminars, and most had limited hours attending seminars. Based on the information interview, this training occurred three 2 to 3 years ago.

Table 7. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Teacher – Respondents in the Number of Hours of Seminar/Training Attended

Number of Hours of Seminar/Training Attended	Frequency	Percentage
Below 9 Hours	3	60 %
9 – 40 Hours	2	40 %
Total	5	100 %

Table 8 shows the Extent of utilization of small-group learning adopted by the teachers in Mathematics. The indicators that were rated were the following: small group discussion consists of 4 – 5 members, which enables all members to talk/share their ideas among themselves; assuring that there must be a leader who coordinates the discussion but does not necessarily do the discussion; assigning a recorder or secretary to record the proceedings of the group discussion who is called the rapporteur; letting no one among the group to supposedly get out of the topic that is put up for discussion; ensuring that there is always freedom to ask questions, free exchange of opinions, ideas, and viewpoints related to the topic discussed. On the teacher's stand, the third, fourth, and fifth indicators were rated with a mean of 4.00, 4.20, and 4.20, respectively, with a descriptive value of often. The first indicator was rated 3.40 with a descriptive value of sometimes, while the second indicator was rated 4.40 or permanently by the teachers. From the pupil's point of view, all five indicators were rated as often on the delivery of the strategy. This further implies that the mathematics teacher often uses small group learning as a teaching strategy.

Table 8 Mean Distribution of Extent of Utilization of Small Group Learning Adopted by the Teachers in Mathematics as Assessed by the respondents

Small Group Learning	Teacher Respondents		Pupil Respondents	
	Mean	Descriptive Value	Mean	Descriptive Value
(1) I am forming a small group discussion of 4 – 5 members, enabling all bar members to talk and share their lives.	3.40	Sometimes	4.12	Often
(2) I assure my pupils that a leader must coordinate the discussion rather than necessarily do the discussion.	4.40	Always	3.79	Often
(3) I am assigning a recorder or secretary to record the group discussion proceedings of the rapporteur.	4.00	Often	3.85	Often

(4) I enforce a rule that no group member can leave the topic up for discussion.	4.20	Often	3.84	Often
(5) I always ensure my pupils are free to ask questions and exchange ideas and viewpoints related to the topic discussed.	4.20	Often	3.77	Often
Overall Mean	4.40	Often	3.88	Often

Table 9 depicts the extent to which the Problem-Solving Strategy adopted by the teachers in Mathematics was utilized. As seen in the table, all indicators of the strategy mentioned above were rated by the teachers with a descriptive value of Always. On the other hand, the pupils assessed all the indicators of the problem-solving strategy with a descriptive value of often. The findings were consistent with Biggayan's study (2022). She cited that problem-solving teachers often use problem-solving strategies because they pose a challenge and require pupils to read and comprehend the problem text.

Table 9. Mean Distribution of Extent of Utilization of Problem-Solving Adopted by the Teachers in Mathematics as Assessed by the respondents.

Problem-Solving	Teacher Respondents		Pupil Respondents	
	Mean	Descriptive Value	Mean	Descriptive Value
(1) I always emphasize that before solving the problem, the given conditions and what is asked in the problem should be identified first.	5.00	Always	4.14	Often
(2) I always emphasize that they should check their answer after finding the solution/ answer.	4.80	Always	4.06	Often
(3) I always ensure that the pupil illustrates/draws the figure of the given pr before solving the problem.	4.80	Always	4.07	Often
(4) I always advise my pupils to look for a typical pattern or a simple problem, like the given problem, before solving the given problem.	4.80	Always	4.07	Often
(5) I always ask my pupils to do drills, exercises, or enrichment activities until they understand the topic.	5.00	Always	3.84	Often
Overall Mean	4.88	Always	4.04	Often

Table 10 illustrates the extent of utilization of Models/Manipulatives adopted by the teachers in Mathematics. The cited indicators were the following: using a model like a weighing scale, maps, and other manipulatives to help my pupils understand the lesson; using a model or manipulatives to illustrate complex concepts to help my pupils understand them easily; Manipulating the miniatures or specimens represent the actual object; using physical objects that are used as teaching tools to engage pupils in the hands-on learning of mathematics; using models/manipulatives to introduce, practice, or remediate some misconception my pupils committed. The teachers assessed the indicators as 3.40 or sometimes, 3.60 or often, 4.40 or always, 4.20 or often, and 4.20 or often, respectively. While the pupils assessed all the indicators with a descriptive value of often. The study by Boggan (2010) explains the importance and benefits of Mathematics manipulation. For decades, the National Council for Teachers in Mathematics has encouraged school districts nationwide to use manipulative in mathematical instruction. The value of manipulation has been recognized for many years, but some teachers are reluctant to use them in their lessons. Throughout Boggan's study, a discussion of the positive results of several research studies strongly suggests the use of manipulation is suggested. The history and advancement of manipulation are discussed and introduced to pupils in the correct way to use them.

According to Clements and Sowell, as cited by Biggayan (2022), manipulatives increase pupils' mathematics achievement. When manipulatives are employed in mathematics classes, pupils are more active, their motivation for learning is higher, and they can adopt a positive attitude towards mathematics lessons.

Table 10 Mean Distribution of Extent of utilization of Using Models/Manipulative Adopted by the Teachers in Mathematics as Assessed by the respondents

Using Models/Manipulative	Teacher Respondents		Pupil Respondents	
	Mean	Descriptive Value	Mean	Descriptive Value
(1) I use a model like a weighing scale, maps, and other manipulatives to help my pupils understand the lesson.	3.40	Sometimes	4.06	Often
(2) I use a model or manipulatives to illustrate complex concepts to help my pupils understand them easily.	3.60	Often	3.86	Often
(3) I am Manipulating the miniatures or specimens to represent the real object.	4.40	Always	3.67	Often
(4) I am using physical objects as teaching tools to engage pupils in hands-on mathematics learning.	4.20	Often	3.71	Often
(5) I am using models/manipulatives to introduce, practice, or remediate some misconceptions my pupils committed.	4.20	Often	4.04	Often
Overall Mean	3.96	Often	3.87	Often

Table 11 displays the extent to which teachers utilized games in mathematics teaching. From a teacher's perspective, they assessed three out of five indicators with a descriptive value of often, while the other two were rated as sometimes and always. Meanwhile, the pupils assessed all five indicators with a descriptive value of often. According to Dede, as cited by Biggayan (2022), games can create local contexts that can similarly engage learners, whether at home, in school, or after-school programs. In formal education, the teacher requires the pupils to interact with the game, and the pupils may or may not be motivated. In informal contexts, individuals play a game for fun, motivated by their interest and enjoyment.

Table 11 Mean Distribution of Extent of utilization of Games Adopted by the Teachers in Mathematics as Assessed by the respondents

Using Games	Teacher Respondents		Pupil Respondents	
	Mean	Descriptive Value	Mean	Descriptive Value
(1) I use a locally popular game in my class to help my pupils enjoy and understand the lesson.	3.60	Sometimes	3.36	Often
(2) I am letting my pupils play a bingo game to strengthen and deepen their understanding of the lesson.	3.60	Often	3.99	Often
(3) I am creating a cross-word puzzle and letting my pupils do it so they can easily understand the topic.	4.00	Always	3.77	Often

(4) I am doing everything to make my discussion more efficient and effective, including making games that encourage my pupils to be more participative.	4.40	Often	3.80	Often
(5) I ensure all my pupils enjoy the session by integrating games like bingo, cross-crosswords, and other games into the discussion.	4.40	Often	3.55	Often
Overall Mean	4.00	Often	3.49	Often

Table 12 shows the summary table of the statistical results of the extent of innovative teaching strategies adopted by the teachers in Mathematics as assessed by the respondents. It is reflected in the table that Small Group Learning, using Models/Manipulatives and games, was rated often as a strategy in teaching Mathematics with means of 4.40, 3.96, and 4.00; meanwhile, enjoyable-solving strategies problem-solving strategies in teaching Mathematics were consistently rated always with a mean of 4.88, as assessed by the teachers. On the other hand, the pupils assessed small group learning, problem-solving, using models/ manipulatives and games with a descriptive value of often as strategies in teaching mathematics with means of 3.88, 4.04, 3.87, and 3.49, respectively. The four innovative teaching often rated as a strategy study have an overall mean of 4.31 or more often, as assessed by the teachers, while the pupils' overall mean is 3.82 or more often. This implies that teachers often send teachers to use innovative teaching strategies, e., small Group Learning, problem-solving, Models/Manipulatives, and Games teaching Mathematics.

Table 12 Summary Table of the Statistical Results of the Extent of Innovative Teaching Strategies Adopted by the Teachers in Mathematics as Assessed by the Respondents

Innovative Teaching Strategy	Teacher Respondents		Pupil Respondents	
	Mean	Descriptive Value	Mean	Descriptive Value
Small Group Learning	4.40	Often	3.88	Often
Problem-Solving	4.88	Always	4.04	Often
Using Models/Manipulatives	3.96	Often	3.87	Often
Games	4.00	Often	3.49	Often
Overall Mean	4.31	Often	3.82	Often

Table 13 presents the relationship between the profile of teacher respondents and their extent of utilization of the small group learning strategy. The teacher respondents' profiles were used to test the relationship between the small group learning strategy. The profiles of the teacher respondents include age, sex, marital status, highest educational attainment, years of teaching mathematics, and seminars attended. The table shows that the said profiles have a p-value more significant than the significance level, which is $\alpha = 0.05$.; thus, the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This implies that teachers have nothing to do with the extent of utilization of the Small Group Learning strategy.

Table 13 Test of the relationship between the profile of teacher respondents and their extent of utilization of the Small Group Learning strategy

Teachers' Profile	χ^2	p-value	decision
Age	6.669 ^a	0.353	Not Significant
Sex	4.434 ^a	0.209	Not Significant
Marital Status	2.477 ^a	0.479	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	6.233 ^a	0.398	Not Significant
Years of Teaching Mathematics	4.222 ^a	0.238	Not Significant
Seminars Attended	0.796 ^a	0.850	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 14 shows the relationship between the profile of teacher respondents and their extent of utilization of the problem-solving strategy. Age, sex, marital status, highest Educational Attainment, years of teaching mathematics, and seminars attended are the profiles of teacher respondents' profiles used to test the relationship between the problem-solving strategy with an $\alpha = 0.05$ significance level. The table shows that the computed p-values for age and seminars attended are 0.208 and 0.665, which is insufficient to reject the null hypothesis. It further implies that the extent of utilization of the problem-solving strategy does not depend on the age and seminars attended by the teacher respondents. However, the computed p-values—the value of sex is 0.004; Marital Status is 0.000, highest educational attainment is 0.016, and years of teaching mathematics values are all less than the significance level at 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. The result suggests that the extent to which the problem-solving strategy is utilized is affected by the teachers' sex, marital status, highest educational attainment, and Years of Teaching Mathematics.

Table 14 Test of the relationship between the profile of teacher respondents and their extent of using the Problem-Solving strategy

Teachers' Profile	χ^2	p-value	decision
Age	5.881 ^a	0.208	Not Significant
Sex	10.990 ^a	0.004	Significant
Marital Status	15.549 ^a	0.000	Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	12.261 ^a	0.016	Significant
Years of Teaching Mathematics	12.108 ^a	0.02	Significant
Seminars Attended	0.816 ^a	0.665	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 15 presents the difference between the profiles of teacher respondents and the extent to which models/manipulative strategies are utilized in teaching mathematics. The study included profiles on age, sex, marital status, highest educational attainment, years of teaching, and seminar attendance. The table shows that the computed p-values for marital status and seminars attended are 0.054 and 0.936, respectively, more significant than the significance level of 0.05. This suggests that teachers' marital status and seminars attended are not significant in their extent of utilization of models/manipulatives as a strategy in teaching mathematics. However, the remaining teachers' profiles have a computed p-value less than the level of significance at 0.05. This implies that the extent of using models/manipulatives as a strategy is greater than the significance of status and years of teaching mathematics.

Table 15 Test of the relationship between the profile of teacher respondents and their extent of utilization of Models/manipulatives strategy

Teachers' Profile	χ^2	p-value	decision
Age	15.513 ^a	0.004	Significant
Sex	17.456 ^a	0.000	Significant
Marital Status	5.843 ^a	0.054	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	18.842 ^a	0.001	Significant
Years of Teaching Mathematics	16.597 ^a	0.000	Significant
Seminars Attended	0.132 ^a	0.936	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 16 reveals the relationship between the profile of teacher respondents and their extent of using Games as a strategy in teaching mathematics subjects. It shows that age affects the extent of using games as a strategy. However, teachers' teacher profiles, such as sex, marital status, highest educational attainment, years of teaching mathematics, and seminars attended, have a computed p-value—value more significant than the alpha at 0.05. This implies that these profiles do not affect the extent of utilization of the said strategy.

Table 16 Test of the relationship between the profile of teacher respondents and their extent of utilization of Games.

Teachers' Profile	χ^2	p-value	decision
Age	15.689 ^a	0.047	Significant
Sex	8.856 ^a	0.065	Not Significant
Marital Status	0.877 ^a	0.928	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	10.717 ^a	0.218	Not Significant
Years of Teaching Mathematics	7.359 ^a	0.118	Not Significant
Seminars Attended	4.840 ^a	0.304	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 17 reveals the frequency and percentage distribution of Academic Performance of pupil – respondents during the first grading grade of the school year 2019 – 2020. It also illustrates that 42.2 %, or 65 of the respondents got a grade ranging from 75 – 79, followed by 27, or 17.5 % of them, having a grade interval of 8 – 84, grade interval of 90 – 100, and below 74 have the same frequency of 21 or 13.6 %, and 20 or 13.0 % of the respondents' grades range from 85 – 89. It also shows that the computed mean of the respondent's Academic Performance in Mathematics is 80.35, with a descriptive value of satisfactory.

Table 17. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Pupil – Respondent's Academic Performance in Mathematics

Grades Interval	Frequency	Percentage	Proficiency Level
90 – 100	21	13.6 %	Outstanding
85 – 89	20	13.0 %	Very Satisfactory
80 – 84	27	17.5 %	Satisfactory
75 – 79	65	42.2 %	Fairly Satisfactory
Below 74	21	13.6 %	Did Not Meet Expectations
Total	154	100 %	

Mean = 80.35

Table 18 presents the relationship between the extent to which innovative teaching strategies are utilized and pupils' academic performance in Mathematics. The innovative teaching strategies included are small group Learning, Problem Solving, Models/Manipulatives, and Games. It reveals that the computed p-values–values for the innovative teaching strategies are 0.999, 0.880, 0.572, and 0.492, respectively, more significant than the alpha at 0.05. This implies that the given innovative teaching strategies do not affect the pupils' academic performance in Mathematics.

Table 18. Test of the relationship between the extent of utilization of innovative teaching strategies and Pupils' academic performance values for forces.

Variables	r – value	p-value	Depression
Small Group Learning	0.000	0.999	Not Significant
Problem-Solving	–0.012	0.880	Not Significant
Models/Manipulatives	–0.046	0.572	Not Significant
domes	0.056	0.492	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Discussion

This study, conducted in the Baggao West District, demonstrates the effectiveness of creative math teaching strategies. It specifically examined the impact of problem-solving, small group learning, models or manipulatives, and games on student academic performance in this district. The results show that most teachers use problem-solving activities to get students interested. This backs up other research

about problem-solving in math classes; it helps students think critically and use real-life math concepts (Biggayan, 2022). The fact that teachers use problem-solving all the time may show how useful it is for handling students' different levels of information and helping them learn more deeply. Some classes used games, models or manipulatives, and small group learning, but not all did. Even if teachers know these strategies could work, they need to improve at solving problems as in regular schooling. Because they need the skills or materials, some teachers might hesitate to use models and manipulatives, even though they help students understand and interact with abstract mathematical ideas (Soriano, 2022).

One important finding was that teachers' sex, marriage status, level of education, and number of years of experience had a significant impact on the use of certain problem-solving and modeling/manipulative strategies. These strategies worked better with more experienced teachers, showing how crucial professional growth is for improving teaching methods. Surprisingly, the study found that gender and marriage status had the most significant effects on strategy use. This shows that social or cultural factors affect how and what students like to learn, but more research is needed to be sure of this. There was, however, no significant link between teacher traits and games and small group learning. This suggests that these methods may be used more often, regardless of the teacher's experience. The need for further research in this area is evident, and educators are encouraged to contribute to this ongoing learning process.

The study that found a strong link between creative ways of teaching and student success is fascinating. This goes against the idea that the way we teach now makes students smarter. These strategies get students more involved or make learning fun but might not help them get better grades. According to research, what motivates students, what they already know, and their learning surroundings significantly impact their academic success compared to how they are taught (Livingston & Borko, 1990). These new ideas also help students think more critically and solve problems better, which should be appropriately evaluated in student performance reviews.

Conclusion

Various teaching strategies help pupils take more responsibility for their learning, and teachers are enhanced in the teaching process. The key is to create more interactive learning environments more interactive learning environments, integrate technology into the learning experience, and use games as a learning strategy when appropriate. Though teachers are familiar with these methods, their consistent use provides room for improvement. More effective mathematics teaching will rely mainly on a knowledge of how to balance many strategies to manage the cognitive and emotional aspects of learning. Their impact on academic performance still needs clarification, even if Baggao West District teachers use innovative teaching strategies. The study underlines the necessity of more all-encompassing techniques to evaluate how various approaches influence numerous facets of pupil education and the need for teacher training.

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